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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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SESSION XII

XII - INTEGRATED PEST MANAGEMENT

POSTER

Agroecological management of processing tomato crop pests in Campania: effect of inter-cropping, border-cropping, and root symbionts on the control of *Phthorimaea (=Tuta) absoluta* and on the biodiversity of the agricultural system

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Reducing chemical inputs to control biotic adversities has become a priority in agricultural systems to mitigate the potential negative environmental effects and to preserve increasingly scarce water resources. The agroecological approach to crop management offers an alternative to conventional methods by promoting the conservation and enhancement of functional biodiversity both above and below ground. In line with this principle, in the framework of the PRIMA project "ASTER - Agroecology-inspired Strategies and Tools to Enhance Resilience and Ecosystem Services in Tomato Crop", a study was conducted on a commercial crop of processing tomato, combining inter-cropping with repellent plants, the use of root symbionts, and the increase, around the perimeter of the crop, of vegetation biodiversity (border-cropping). The goal was to establish a resilient growing system capable of reducing the pest impact, with a particular focus on *Phthorimaea absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), a key pest of processing tomato crops in Campania. The experiment was conducted in an area with intensive open-field horticulture, characterized by a significant depletion of spontaneous vegetation. Inter-cropping was implemented by transplanting *Tagetes patula* along the double rows of the tomato crop. This plant is known for its nematicide properties and has demonstrated repellency against *P. absoluta* and whiteflies in laboratory studies. Vegetation biodiversity was further increased by sowing a mixture of flowering herbaceous plants in perimeter strips to create refuge and feeding areas for natural enemies and pollinators. Additionally, *Calendula* and *Verbena* plants, known to support predatory mirids (the primary natural enemies of *P. absoluta*) for reproduction and feeding, were transplanted at the crop edges. As root symbionts, specific *Trichoderma* strains, selected at CNR-IPSP for their biostimulant effects on tomato plants, were applied. No insecticide treatments were applied during the crop cycle. The ASTER plot, managed under an agroecological approach, was compared to a conventional control plot (lacking vegetation biodiversity and treated with synthetic insecticides). Periodic monitoring of insect populations revealed that, compared to the conventional control, the ASTER plot showed a significant reduction in pest infestation, particularly of *P. absoluta*, and a considerable increase in both the diversity and abundance of natural antagonists. The biodiversity of the cropping system was also assessed using Malaise traps, which showed a significantly higher abundance and diversity of Hymenoptera parasitoids and predatory insects in the ASTER plot compared to the conventional control, both in terms of number of individual and number of families and species sampled. These results, currently being replicated, highlight that the agroecological approach for the management of processing tomato pests, even in areas with intensive agriculture, can be an environmentally and economically sustainable solution.

KEYWORDS: agroecology, biodiversity, Hymenoptera, parasitoids, predators, IPM, *Tagetes*, *Trichoderma*